

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Annotation: Resistance to strong competition, which in the conditions of market relations occupies a priority place in the labor market, requires each specialist to possess professional competence, consistently improve it. So what is competence? Here we will talk about these and related ideas.

Keywords: Competence, social competence, special competence, types of competencies.

The concept of "competence" has entered the field of education as a result of scientific research by psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence refers to "unconventional situations, how a specialist behaves in unexpected cases, enters into communication, takes a new course in interaction with opponents, takes on ambiguous tasks, uses information full of contradictions, owns a plan of action in consistently developing and complex processes."

Professional competence implies not the acquisition of special knowledge, qualifications by a specialist, but the assimilation of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction.

Competence also assumes the constant enrichment of specialist knowledge, the study of new information, the ability to understand important social requirements, the search for new information, their processing and application in their activities

Below is a brief overview of the essence of reflective qualities on the basis of professional competence.

1. Social competence-the ability to show activity in social relations, the possession of skills, the ability to enter into communication with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence-preparation for the organization of professional-pedagogical activities, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, real assessment of the results of their activities, which in itself represent the following content:

1) psychological competence – able to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, organize positive communication with students and other participants in the educational process, be able to timely understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts;

2) methodological competence – methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correct definition of forms of educational or educational activity, ability to choose methods and tools for their intended purpose, effective application of methods, successful application of tools;

3) informational competence – the search, collection, sorting, processing and use of necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment, purposeful, appropriate, effective;

4) creative competence-a critical and creative approach to pedagogical activity, being able to demonstrate that it has the skills of creativity;

5) innovative competence-promotion of new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, improving the effectiveness of the educational process, successfully applying them to practice;

6) communicative competence is the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants in the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive effect on them.

7) technological competence – mastering advanced technologies that enrich professional and pedagogical BKM, being able to use modern tools, techniques and technologies.

In the work of pedagogists, various aspects and components have been distinguished and studied, which make it possible to study competence more broadly and thoroughly from the pedagogical point of view.

The following definitions of competence are provided by Shishov:

-general competence based on knowledge, experience, values and inclinations acquired due to learning;

-the ability to establish a connection between knowledge and situations, to find a solution that suits the problem (to say that competence is permissible only if it is manifested in a single situation, unrepresented competence is a big statement, even if it remains hidden possibilities, and not competence).

V.V. Bashev argues that competencies are the individual ability of a person, which is manifested in the street acquisition of this ability to other conditions at a time when conditions change. Areas of application determine their specificity and accuracy (mathematical, linguistic, political and other competencies).

A person who acts effectively in the field of community learning should be able to: that is, a person with competencies:

- 1) be able to research the situation in which he fell;
- 2) be able to establish communication with other people;
- 3) can make decisions;
- 4) be able to organize individual and collective actions to implement the decisions made;
- 5) the ability to master new methods of activity.

Thus, competency can be interpreted as the result of competency, readiness, possession of opportunity and, at the same time, a gloomy action. In other words, competence is a category of activity that is manifested in the process of professional, social and other activities of the subject aimed at performing the tasks set.

Competence means a certain degree of formation of certain qualifications and professional experiences of the individual in relation to their interaction with the objects and subjects around them, necessary for the successful functioning of the individual in society as a whole and in the professional sphere in particular.

The list of significant signs includes knowledge of the basics of Information Technology, the use of a computer as a necessary technical tool, the expression of the

active social position and motivation of the subjects of the educational space, the totality of knowledge, skills and qualifications related to the search, analysis and use of information. Typically, when researching specific competency formation problems, three levels of information - communicative competence acquisition are distinguished:

-base (base) - at this level, the base knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for computer literacy are formed; the minimum use of ICT in the organization of professional activities (the acquisition of common methods of creating, editing, storing, copying and copying information in electronic form, the provision of information through the means of presentation technologies, the acquisition of information search skills in the internet network and x.k., choosing a method (or a combination of these) of interaction in the network that is increasingly consistent with the nature of the problem and allows it to be solved by increasingly optimal methods;

- technological (at this level, ICT becomes an instrument of practical activity (assessment of the potential of internet resources, their interactivity and informativeness from a targeted point of view; analysis of global computer network resources and software tools taking into account the main technological, economic, ergonomic and technical requirements; analysis of the quality, tools and forms of providing software-technological and information;

-to be qualified to create new tools for the implementation of professional activities at the practical (professional) level and to use them effectively in educational processes.

REFERENCES:

1. N. Mamatova, M. Sobirjonova, A. Abdurahimov, Sh. Sharobiddinova BEDEUTUNG UND BESONDERHEITEN LITERATUR // **International Conference on Developments in Education Hosted from Bursa, Turkey March. 20th 2023.**

2. R. Mamatov, Sh. Abduxoshimova, I. Akbarova, G. Nomonova DIE SPEZIFISCHE HISTORISCHE BEDEUTUNG DER DEUTSCHEN

PHONETIK// International Conference on Developments in Education
Hosted from Saint Petersburg, Russia March 23rd 2023

3. N. Mamatova Aspects of Achieving Efficiency in the Educational Process
on the Basis of an Innovative Approach// Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic
Teaching. Journal impact factor: 8.115 ISSN (E): 2795-739X, Volume 15, p 235,
December 2022.

4. R. Mamatov Education and Training in Foreign Countries// Eurasian
Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. Journal impact factor: 8.115 ISSN (E):
2795-739X, Volume 15, p 239, December 2022.

5. R.R.Mamatov THE CONCEPT SPHERE OF HERTA MÜLLER'S
METAPHORIC CREATION// 13th- International Conference on Research in
Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education, Hosted from Berlin, Germany, p 89
April 27th 2023.